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CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

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BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA ICHKI AUDIT METODOLOGIYASI: XALQARO STANDARTLAR VA MILLIY AMALIYOTNING QIYOSIY TAHLILI

Saitmuratov Saitmumarat Masharip o'g'li

Abu Rayhon Beruniy nomidagi Urganch davlat universiteti dotsenti, PhD

E-mail: saitmuratovsaitmumarat@gmail.com

ORCID: 0009-0008-2048-319X

Annotatsiya. Maqolada budget tashkilotlarida ichki audit metodologiyasining ilmiy-nazariy va me'yoriy manbalari — IIA Global ichki audit standartlari (2024), INTOSAI kasbiy hujjatlar tizimi (IFPP) hamda O'zbekistonning idoraviy-normativ asoslari qiyosiy tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda etalon mezonlar bo'yicha muvofiqlikni baholash usuli qo'llanilgan. Asosiy natija shundan iboratki, O'zbekistonda ichki auditning institutsional asosi xalqaro tamoyillarga muvofiq shakllantirilgan, biroq yagona kodlashtirilgan milliy ichki audit standartining yo'qligi metodologik chuqurlikni va ichki auditning assurans hamda maslahat qiymatini cheklaydi. Muammoni bartaraf etish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ichki audit, davlat moliyaviy nazorati, budget tashkiloti, IIA standartlari, INTOSAI, ISSAI, GUID, milliy standart, metodologiya, budget intizomi, hisobdorlik, shaffoflik.

Аннотация. В статье проведён сравнительный анализ научно-теоретических и нормативных источников методологии внутреннего аудита в бюджетных организациях: Глобальных стандартов внутреннего аудита IIA (2024), системы профессиональных документов INTOSAI (IFPP) и ведомственно-нормативной базы Узбекистана. Использован метод оценки соответствия по эталонным критериям. Основной вывод: институциональная основа внутреннего аудита в Узбекистане сформирована в соответствии с международными принципами, однако отсутствие единого кодифицированного национального стандарта внутреннего аудита ограничивает методологическую глубину и ценность аудита. Разработаны рекомендации по устранению данного пробела.

Ключевые слова: внутренний аудит, государственный финансовый контроль, бюджетная организация, стандарты IIA, INTOSAI, ISSAI, GUID, национальный стандарт, методология, бюджетная дисциплина, подотчётность, прозрачность.

Abstract. The article provides a comparative analysis of the scientific, theoretical and regulatory sources of internal audit methodology in budget organizations: the IIA Global Internal Audit Standards (2024), the INTOSAI Framework of Professional Pronouncements (IFPP), and Uzbekistan's departmental-regulatory base. A benchmark-based conformance assessment method is applied. The main finding is that the institutional foundation of internal audit in Uzbekistan has been built in line with international principles, yet the absence of a single codified national internal audit standard limits methodological depth and the assurance and advisory value of internal audit. Recommendations are proposed to close this gap.

Keywords: internal audit, state financial control, budget organization, IIA standards, INTOSAI, ISSAI, GUID, national standard, methodology, budget discipline, accountability, transparency.

KIRISH

Davlat moliyaviy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish zamonaviy davlat boshqaruvining markaziy vazifalaridan biridir. So'nggi yillarda davlat moliyaviy nazorati jazolovchi va post-faktum yondashuvdan xavf-xatarlarni oldindan baholashga va profilaktikaga qaratilgan ichki audit modeliga o'tmoqda. O'zbekistonda 2021–2022-yillarda amalga oshirilgan islohotlar — davlat moliyaviy nazorati tizimini takomillashtirish, mustaqil ichki audit xizmatlarini tashkil etish va nazorat tadbirlarini yagona elektron tizimda qayd etish — ushbu o'zgarishlarning huquqiy va institutsional negizini yaratdi [2;3].

Biroq ichki audit faoliyatining sifati uning institutsional mavjudligi bilan emas, balki tayanadigan metodologik asoslari bilan belgilanadi. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ichki audit metodologiyasining manbalarini — ichki audit bo'yicha xalqaro standartlar, davlat sektori auditiga oid INTOSAI hujjatlari va milliy normativ baza — tizimli tahlil qilish dolzarb ilmiy muammodir.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi — budget tashkilotlarida ichki audit metodologiyasining xalqaro va milliy manbalarini qiyosiy tahlil qilish, ularning muvofiqlik darajasini baholash va mavjud bo'shliqlarni bartaraf etish bo'yicha

tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi shundaki, unda milliy ichki audit modeli xalqaro etalon-mezonlar tizimi asosida baholanib, metodologik kodlashtirish bo'shlig'i asoslab beriladi va uni bartaraf etish yo'nalishlari taklif etiladi.

MAVZUGA OID ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI

Budjet tashkilotlarida ichki audit metodologiyasini shakllantirish va uni xalqaro standartlar bilan qiyosiy tahlil qilish masalasi bir necha darajadagi manbalarni o'z ichiga oladi: xalqaro professional standartlar, milliy qonunchilik va normativ hujjatlar hamda ilmiy tadqiqotlar. Ushbu adabiyotlar majmui qiyosiy tahlil uchun zarur bo'lgan nazariy asos, huquqiy baza va amaliy kontekstni taqdim etadi.

Xalqaro darajada ichki audit metodologiyasining eng muhim asosi The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) tomonidan 2024-yilda qabul qilingan Global Internal Audit Standards (2025-yil 1-sentabrdan kuchga kiradi) hisoblanadi. Ushbu standart mustaqillik, obyektivlik, riskka asoslangan yondashuv, professionallik va doimiy takomillashtirish tamoyillariga asoslangan bo'lib, ichki auditning majburiy elementlari (audit rejasi, ishchi hujjatlar, axloq kodeksi) va ularni qo'llash talablarini belgilaydi. Qiyosiy tahlilda ushbu standart asosiy namunaviy model vazifasini bajaradi — milliy hujjatlar shu standartga yaqinlik darajasida baholanadi. Davlat sektori kontekstida esa INTOSAI (Xalqaro oliy audit institutlari tashkiloti)ning professional bayonotlari — IFPP (INTOSAI-P, ISSAI, GUID) tizimi muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu tizim davlat sektori auditi uchun alohida konseptual asosni taqdim etadi. Ayniqsa, ISSAI 100 “Davlat sektori auditi asosiy tamoyillari”da mustaqillik, xolislik, kasbiy mahorat, maxfiylik, ishonchlilik va sifat kabi tamoyillar davlat sektori kontekstida talqin qilingan. Qiyosiy tahlilda ISSAI 100 orqali milliy namunaviy nizomdagi tamoyillarning to'liqligi, aniqligi va qo'llanilish imkoniyatlari tekshiriladi. Yana bir muhim xalqaro asos — COSO (Treadway komissiyasi homiylik tashkilotlari qo'mitasi) tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan “Ichki nazorat — integratsiyalashgan ramka” modelidir. COSO modeli ichki audit metodologiyasining beshta asosiy komponenti — nazorat muhiti, riskni baholash, nazorat tadbirlari, axborot va kommunikatsiya hamda monitoringni belgilaydi. Qiyosiy tahlilda ushbu tizimli yondashuv mezonlari sifatida qo'llaniladi — O'zbekistonning amaldagi metodologiyasida ushbu komponentlar qay darajada aks etgani tahlil qilinadi.

Milliy darajada esa, birinchi navbatda, O'zbekiston Respublikasining Budjet kodeksi (2013-yil 26-dekabr, amaldagi tahrir) budjet jarayonining asosiy qonuni bo'lib, budjet tashkilotlarida ichki audit metodologiyasining huquqiy maydonini belgilaydi [1]. Kodeksda budjet intizomi, maqsadli va samarali sarflanish, nazoratning turlari qayd etilgan bo'lib, qiyosiy tahlilda ushbu hujjat milliy metodologiyaning huquqiy darajasi va chegaralarini aniqlash uchun asos bo'ladi — xalqaro standartlarda talab qilinadigan mustaqillik va riskka asoslangan yondashuv milliy qonunchilikda qay darajada aks etganini ko'rsatadi. 2021-yil 27-avgustdagi PF-6300-son Farmon “Davlat moliyaviy nazorati tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida” ichki audit tizimini isloh qilishning strategik hujjati hisoblanadi [2]. Unda ichki audit xizmatlarini joriy etish, ularning mustaqilligini oshirish, xalqaro standartlarga moslashtirish kabi yo'nalishlar belgilangan. Farmon milliy amaliyotdagi institutsional islohotlar yo'nalishini aks ettiradi — qiyosiy tahlilda xalqaro tamoyillarni qabul qilishga tayyorlik darajasini baholash uchun muhim manba hisoblanadi. Budjet tashkilotlaridagi ichki audit faoliyatini bevosita tartibga soluvchi asosiy hujjat — O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2022-yil 1-avgustdagi 416-son qarori bilan tasdiqlangan “Davlat organlari va tashkilotlarining ichki audit xizmati to'g'risidagi namunaviy nizom” hisoblanadi [3]. Ushbu nizomda ichki audit xizmatining vazifalari, tuzilmasi, huquq va majburiyatlari, hisobot berish tartibi belgilangan. Namunaviy xususiyat tufayli metodologiya tashkilotlar darajasida farqlanishi mumkin. Qiyosiy tahlilda ushbu hujjat IIA va INTOSAI standartlari bilan tashkiliy mustaqillik, resurslar bilan ta'minlash, malaka talablari bo'yicha solishtiriladi. Kadrlar malakasi masalasida Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2021-yil 5-maydagi 280-son qarori (ichki audit xodimlarini sertifikatlash tartibi to'g'risida) muhim ahamiyatga ega [4]. Sertifikatlash tizimi professional kadrlar tayyorlash va ularning malakasini baholash mexanizmini belgilaydi. Xalqaro standartlar (IIA, INTOSAI) ham kompetensiya va uzluksiz ta'limni talab qiladi. Qiyosiy tahlilda O'zbekiston modelining sertifikatlash mezonlari, attestatsiya davriyligi va tan olish tizimi global talablarga qanchalik yaqinligi o'rganiladi. So'nggi yillarda qabul qilingan muhim hujjatlardan biri — Vazirlar Mahkamasining 2023-yil 14-avgustdagi 377-son qarori (ichki audit xizmatlari faoliyatini baholash tartibi to'g'risida) [5]. Ushbu nisbatan yangi hujjat ichki audit sifatini tashqi (nazorat qiluvchi organlar tomonidan) va ichki baholash mexanizmlarini joriy etadi. IIA standartlarida sifatni baholashning majburiy tashqi tekshiruv (External Quality Assessment) talab qilinadi. Qiyosiy tahlilda O'zbekiston modelining baholash usullari, davriyligi va mustaqillik darajasi xalqaro talablar bilan taqqoslanadi.

Ilmiy tadqiqotlar darajasida esa Xamidova Z.U. (2020) tomonidan “Budjet tashkilotlarida moliyaviy nazorat va ichki audit xizmati faoliyatini takomillashtirish” nomli asari alohida o'rin tutadi. Mazkur ilmiy ish O'zbekiston sharoitida budjet tashkilotlari ichki auditining amaliy holatini, muammolarini va rivojlanish yo'nalishlarini o'rganadi. Muallif tomonidan aniqlangan xalqaro standartlarni joriy etishdagi qiyinchiliklar, malaka yetishmovchiligi, metodologik birlikning yo'qligi kabi muammolar qiyosiy tahlil uchun amaliy kontekst beradi. Ushbu tadqiqot

milliy amaliyotning “haqiqiy holati”ni aks ettirgan holda, xalqaro standartlar bilan oradagi farqlar va tafovutlarni aniq misollarda ko‘rsatadi. Shunday qilib, keltirilgan adabiyotlar majmui — xalqaro standartlar (IIA, INTOSAI, COSO), milliy normativ hujjatlar (Budget kodeksi, Prezident farmoni, Vazirlar Mahkamasining qarorlari) va ilmiy tadqiqot — birgalikda budget tashkilotlarida ichki audit metodologiyasini xalqaro standartlar va milliy amaliyot nuqtai nazaridan qiyosiy tahlil qilish uchun to‘liq va tizimli asosni tashkil etadi.

TADQIQOT METODOLOGIYASI

Metodologik jihatdan tadqiqotda nazariy umumlashtirish, huquqiy kontent-tahlil va qiyosiy tahlil usullari qo‘llanildi. Markaziy tahliliy vosita sifatida etalon mezonlar bo‘yicha muvofiqlikni baholash usuli ishlatildi: yetti asosiy mezon (mustaqillik, etika va kompetentlik, xavf asosida rejalashtirish, metodologik kodlashtirish, sifat ta‘minoti, assurans va maslahat balansi, raqamlashtirish) bo‘yicha xalqaro talab milliy holat bilan solishtirilib, muvofiqlik darajasi “yuqori”, “qisman” yoki “bo‘shliq” sifatida baholandi. Manba bazasini xalqaro standartlar hamda O‘zbekiston Respublikasining normativ-huquqiy hujjatlari (PF-6300, Vazirlar Mahkamasining 416-son qarori va tegishli nizomlari) tashkil etdi [2;3].

TAHLIL VA NATIJALAR

Ichki audit metodologiyasining manbalari uch qatlamdan iborat: xalqaro metodologik etalonlar (IIA va INTOSAI), ularga tayanuvchi milliy idoraviy-normativ asoslar hamda amaliy realizatsiya. Ushbu qatlamlar va ular o‘rtasidagi munosabat 1-rasmda umumlashtirilgan.

1-rasm. Ichki audit metodologiyasining manbalari va milliy realizatsiya modeli

Etalon-mezonlar bo‘yicha muvofiqlikni baholash natijalari 1-jadvalda keltirilgan. Tahlil shuni ko‘rsatadiki, mustaqillik, hisobdorlik chizig‘i hamda etika va kompetentlik mezonlari bo‘yicha milliy model xalqaro talablarga yuqori darajada muvofiq keladi. Xavf asosida rejalashtirish, sifat ta‘minoti, assurans va maslahat balansi hamda raqamlashtirish bo‘yicha muvofiqlik qisman bo‘lib, rivojlanish bosqichida. Eng sezilarli farq — metodologik kodlashtirish mezonida: O‘zbekistonda audit jarayonining tafsilotlari yagona kodlashtirilgan standart shaklida emas, balki turli nizomlar majmuasi orqali belgilangan.

1-jadval.

Milliy ichki audit metodologiyasining xalqaro etalonlarga muvofiqligi

Mezon	Xalqaro talab (etalon)	Milliy holat	Muvofiqlik bahosi
Mustaqillik va hisobdorlik chizig'i	Boshqaruv organiga bevosita hisobdorlik (IIA Domen III; ISSAI mustaqillik)	Boshqa bo'linmalardan mustaqillik; asosiy faoliyat natijasiga javobgar emas	Yuqori
Etika va kompetentlik	Halollik, xolislik, kompetentlik (ISSAI 130, 150)	Sertifikatlash tartibi joriy; malaka talablari belgilangan	Yuqori
Xavf asosida rejalashtirish	Xavf va ahamiyatlilik asosida (IIA Domen IV)	Xavf tahlili va masofaviy audit qisman qo'llaniladi	Qisman
Metodologik kodlashtirish	Yagona kodlashtirilgan standartlar (domen–tamoyil–standart)	Nizomlar majmuasi; yagona standart yo'q	Bo'shliq
Sifat ta'minoti	Ichki + davriy tashqi baholash	Faoliyatni baholash nizomi mavjud; tashqi baholash cheklangan	Qisman
Assurans + maslahat balansi	Assurans va maslahat funksiyalari uyg'un	Asosan nazorat/profilaktika; maslahat zaif	Qisman
Raqamlashtirish	Ma'lumotlar tahlili, AI vositalari (IIA)	Audit tadbirlari yagona elektron tizimda qayd etiladi	Qisman

Manba: IIA GIAS (2024), INTOSAI IFPP va O'zbekiston normativ hujjatlari asosida muallif tomonidan tuzilgan.

Olingan natijalar O'zbekistondagi islohotlar xalqaro tamoyillarga mos yo'nalishda kechayotganini tasdiqlaydi: mustaqil ichki audit xizmatlarini tashkil etish IIA va INTOSAI mustaqillik talabiga, profilaktik yondashuv esa auditning qiymat qo'shuvchi funksiyasi haqidagi qarashga muvofiqdir. Shu bilan birga, tahlil markaziy muammoni — metodologik kodlashtirish bo'shlig'ini aniqlab beradi. Idoraviy nizomlar ichki auditning maqsadi, tashkiliy tuzilmasi va kadrlar masalalarini belgilaydi, ammo audit tadbirini rejalashtirish, dalil to'plash, ahamiyatlilikni baholash, xulosalash va sifat ta'minoti kabi bevosita metodologik bosqichlarni yagona, qiyoslanadigan standart darajasida tartibga solmaydi.

Ushbu bo'shliqning oqibatlari ikki yo'nalishda namoyon bo'ladi. Birinchidan, metodologik tafsillik yetishmovchiligi audit tadbirlari sifatining tashkilotlararo bir xilligini va natijalar qiyoslanadigan ekanligini kamaytiradi. Ikkinchidan, u ichki auditning maslahat (consulting) funksiyasini cheklab, uni an'anaviy nazorat-tekshiruv faoliyatiga yaqinlashtiradi, natijada auditning assurans bilan birga maslahat orqali yaratadigan to'liq qiymati realizatsiya qilinmaydi. Xalqaro tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, ko'plab mamlakatlar IIA standartlari va INTOSAI ISSAI/GUID hujjatlarini milliy darajada qabul qilish yoki ularga muvofiq milliy standart ishlab chiqish orqali aynan shu bo'shliqni bartaraf etgan.

Tadqiqotning cheklovi shundaki, u nazariy-huquqiy tahlilga tayanadi; muvofiqlik bahosini empirik tasdiqlash uchun audit tadbirlari sifati va natijalari bo'yicha statistik ma'lumotlarga asoslangan kelgusi tadqiqotlar talab etiladi.

XULOSA VA TAKLIFLAR

O'tkazilgan qiyosiy tahlil quyidagi xulosalarga olib keladi. O'zbekistonda budget tashkilotlarida ichki auditning institutsional va huquqiy asosi xalqaro tamoyillarga muvofiq shakllantirilgan; mustaqillik, etika va kadrlar malakasi mezonlari bo'yicha muvofiqlik yuqori. Ayni paytda metodologik kodlashtirish bo'shlig'i — yagona milliy ichki audit standartining yo'qligi — tizimning takomillashtirilishi lozim bo'lgan asosiy jihatlardan biri hisoblanadi va ichki auditning to'liq qiymatini cheklaydi.

Shu asosda quyidagi tavsiyalar ilgari suriladi: 1) IIA Global ichki audit standartlari va INTOSAI ISSAI/GUID hujjatlari asosida xavfga yo'naltirilgan rejalashtirish, dalil to'plash, sifat ta'minoti va hisobot metodologiyasini batafsil belgilovchi yagona milliy ichki audit standartini ishlab chiqish; 2) ichki va davriy tashqi sifat baholash mexanizmini mustahkamlash; 3) assurans bilan bir qatorda maslahat funksiyasini rivojlantirish; 4) ma'lumotlar tahlili va raqamli audit vositalarini kengroq joriy etish hamda auditorlar malakasini xalqaro sertifikatlash talablariga moslashtirish. Ushbu chora-tadbirlar ichki auditni nazorat-tekshiruv vositasidan davlat boshqaruvi sifatini oshiruvchi zamonaviy mexanizmga aylantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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